

Harnessing the Power of PM6:Y6 Semitransparent Photoanodes by Computational Balancement of Photon Absorption in Photoanode/Photovoltaic Organic Tandems: $>7 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ Solar Synthetic Fuels Production at Bias-Free Potentials

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This study first demonstrates the potential of organic photoabsorbing blends in overcoming a critical limitation of metal oxide photoanodes in tandem modules: insufficient photogenerated current. Various organic blends, including PTB7-Th:FOIC, PTB7-Th:O6T-4F, PM6:Y6, and PM6:FM, were systematically tested. When coupled with electron transport layer (ETL) contacts, these blends exhibit exceptional charge separation and extraction, with PM6:Y6 achieving saturation photocurrents up to 16.8 mA cm^{-2} at $1.23 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ (oxygen evolution thermodynamic potential). For the first time, a tandem structure utilizing organic photoanodes has been computationally designed and fabricated and the implementation of a double PM6:Y6 photoanode/photovoltaic structure resulted in photogenerated currents exceeding 7 mA cm^{-2} at 0 V_{RHE} (hydrogen evolution thermodynamic potential) and anodic current onset potentials as low as $-0.5 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$. The herein-presented organic-based approach paves the way for further exploration of different blend combinations to target specific oxidative reactions by selecting precise donor/acceptor candidates among the multiple existing ones.

In the pursuit of efficient PEC devices, tandem photovoltaic-photoelectrochemical (PV-PEC) structures have garnered significant attention over the past decade.^[2,3] These structures are essential for achieving the required potential to drive the desired chemical reactions in bias-free conditions. However, challenges to achieving an efficient energy conversion persist, linked to large bandgaps and high recombination rates associated with metal oxide photoelectrodes, such as BiVO_4 ,^[4–6] WO_3 ,^[7] and TiO_2 ,^[8,9] or metal sulfides like SnS_2 .^[10] These limitations currently constrain the output photocurrent to below 5 mA cm^{-2} , falling short of the targeted 10 mA cm^{-2} for a viable H_2 production. Other semiconductor materials, such as Si ,^[11–13] GaAs ,^[14,15] CIGS ,^[16,17] or CZTS ^[18] lack the transparency needed to form tandem structures to achieve the needed potentials. This underscores the need for innovative approaches to overcome these constraints and enhance the performance of PEC systems in the pursuit of sustainable solar fuel production.^[1,19,20]

1. Introduction

The utilization of solar synthetic fuels, generated through the photoelectrochemical (PEC) conversion of sunlight into chemical bonds, such as H_2 or other CO_2 -based fuels, presents a promising path for achieving long-term efficient energy storage and distribution. Integral to this process are PEC devices,^[1] which consist of semiconductors designed to convert solar light into electricity directly injected into a targeted electrochemical reaction.

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Capitalizing on the recent state-of-the-art advancements in organic photovoltaics (OPV) utilizing bulk heterojunction (BHJ) architectures, employing non-fullerene acceptors (NFA), with tunable band gap and broadband absorption, power conversion efficiencies of 19% in single-junction devices were successfully reached.^[21] Also, NFA are known to be more stable under moisture environments than their fullerene-based counterparts.^[22] This study demonstrated that many NFAs, including Y6, exhibit high resistance to moisture and water immersion. Additionally, it has been shown that blends like PM6:Y6 can be processed in water, achieving excellent photovoltaic performance and operational stability.^[23] Specifically, PM6:Y6 photoanodes have been demonstrated partially stable in moist environments, with their stability further enhanced by the addition of an extra PM6 layer.^[24] Y6-based organic BHJ blends, exemplified by PM6:Y6, have captured considerable interest owing to their exceptional characteristics. These include remarkably low radiative and non-radiative recombination losses, resulting in open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) values of up to 0.84 V .^[25,26] Furthermore, this blend showcases a barrierless free charge generation attributed to the molecular packing of Y6 causing

electron delocalization at the donor/acceptor interface and therefore efficient charge separation.^[27] The extended charge carrier diffusion length observed in this system enhances its performance, while the well-mixed phases contribute to a beneficial morphology, close to optimal for photovoltaic applications.^[28,29] Additionally, the advantages of organic polymers, being devoid of critical elements, and amenable roll-to-roll fabrication processes, result in flexible, lightweight, and semi-transparent products with high upscaling potential.

Although several works have reported the fabrication of organic BHJ-based photoelectrodes,^[22,30] 2 years ago, meaningful anodic photocurrents ($2\text{--}4\text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ at $1.23\text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$) were achieved by applying organic all-polymer donor/acceptor systems such as the PNDITCVT:PBDTTTPD photoactive blend.^[31] Additionally, the authors explored the polymer/small-molecule donor/acceptor systems using the newly synthesized polymer donors PBDT-TPD and PBDTCl-TPD^[32] in photoelectrochemical cells (PEC), denoted as organic PECs (OPECs). These OPEC systems directly interact with water, serving as effective mediums to potentially perform the oxygen evolution reaction (OER). Although a final device would rely on water oxidation without the consumption of sacrificial reagents, the introduction of sacrificial hole scavengers (a sacrificial chemical species having prone redox electrochemical potential and fast kinetics which is oxidized by consuming the holes arriving at the photoanode's surface),^[33] such as SO_3^{2-} , into the electrolyte has facilitated material studies by enhancing the lifetime of the donor/acceptor blend owing to its low oxidative potential and rapid kinetic reaction. Protective PM6^[34] or PM6 + 40 nm Au^[24] layers have been applied when using a NiFeOOH water oxidation catalyst that performed the OER, achieving sustained 4 mA cm^{-2} photocurrents at $1.23\text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ for over 1 h. However, until now, no research has deployed organic-based absorbers with sufficient potential to catalyze the entire water-splitting reaction at significant productive levels.^[35]

In this study we focus on the computational design, experimental fabrication, and characterization of high-throughput OPEC/OPV tandem photoanodes, providing potentials above the required for the water-splitting reaction. PTB7-Th:FOIC, PTB7-Th:O6T-4F, PM6:Y6, and PM6:FM photoanodes are studied, utilizing both nanoparticulate and thin film ZnO electronic transporting layers (ETL). Hole-scavenger oxidation is employed to focus on the photoabsorbing and conversion capabilities of the employed materials and configuration. Among these four, the PM6:Y6-based photoanodes emerge as exceptional performers for oxidative reactions. The transparency of the PM6:Y6 blend has been finely tuned by adjusting the thickness during fabrication, to achieve an optimal light distribution to equilibrate the performance of both elements in tandem series connection while maximizing output photocurrent and photovoltage. Consequently, high-throughput photocurrents ($>7\text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ at 0 V_{RHE} or 16.8 mA cm^{-2} at $1.23\text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$) have been achieved, highlighting the significant promise of all-organic tandem structures for PEC solar fuel production.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Photoanode's Blend Selection

Four different organic blends, namely PTB7-Th:FOIC, PTB7-Th:O6T-4F, PM6:Y6, and PM6:FM, were employed as BHJ photoactive layers in the fabrication of photoanodes. The reason behind exploring these diverse blends lies in the search for candidates exhibiting varying bandgaps or absorption onsets, to subsequently evaluate them individually

as front photoanodes and in a tandem architecture.^[36] Our study involves donor:acceptor blends consisting of two polymer and four non-fullerene acceptors acting as donor and acceptor components, respectively. For this study, we have selected PTB7-Th and PM6 because they are two of the most widely used polymer donors in the OSCs community. PTB7-Th is favored for its red-shifted absorption, making it a good candidate for transparent solar cell applications.^[37] Blends incorporating this donor with FOIC or O6T-4F NFAs have been proven to be effective combinations for achieving top performance in these types of cells.^[28,38] Conversely, PM6 has recently become the benchmark polymer donor due to its strong absorption in the visible range. Pairing with donors like F-M or Y6 results in blends achieving outstanding values of V_{oc} .^[21]

The molecular structure of these organic materials is displayed in **Figure 1a**. Photoanodes were fabricated with the inverted architecture (Glass/ZnO/Active Layer) and to complete the organic photovoltaic (OPV) cell devices, MoO_3 hole transporting layer (HTL) and top Ag contact layers were sequentially added. Details about the fabrication are given in Section S1.2, Supporting Information. The performance of photoanodes based on different organic blends was evaluated at pH 9 and scavenger oxidation conditions, and the results are illustrated in **Figure 1b**.

PTB7-Th:FOIC and PTB7-Th:O6T-4F blends exhibited photocurrents of approximately $8\text{--}9\text{ mA cm}^{-2}$ at $1.23\text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$, with onset voltages at $0.6\text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$, with a slightly better fill factor for the former. In contrast, PM6:FM displayed similar onset voltages, but its photocurrent was reduced by half compared to those from PTB7-Th:FOIC or PTB7-Th:O6T-4F. Such difference is depicted also by the external quantum efficiency of the photoanodes polarized at $1.23\text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ ($\text{EQE}_{1.23\text{V}_{\text{RHE}}}$) spectra (**Figure 1c**), indicating that PM6:FM has a cut-off absorption edge at 740 nm , while PTB7-Th:FOIC, and PTB7-Th:O6T-4F exhibit a cut-off above 930 nm . PM6:Y6 photoanodes displayed superior performance in cyclic voltammetry curves, achieving nearly 15 mA cm^{-2} and an onset voltage of approximately $0.3\text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$, corresponding to a generated photovoltage of roughly $0.8\text{--}0.9\text{ V}$. This value is in agreement with the V_{oc} of 0.84 V obtained for the solar cell structure employing the same blend, as shown in **Figure S2**, Supporting Information. Furthermore, despite the absence in the photoanodes of the reflector back-contact thick silver, commonly used in OPVs to double the light path in the absorber, best-performing samples reached photocurrent values of 16.8 mA cm^{-2} , which represents about two-thirds of the solar cell photocurrent (23.9 mA cm^{-2}). $\text{EQE}_{1.23\text{V}_{\text{RHE}}}$ spectra for PM6:Y6 photoanodes (**Figure 1c**) reveal an exceptional photon-to-electron conversion with an extended tail reaching 940 nm , and quantum efficiencies reaching values up to 60%.

The outstanding difference between the PM6:Y6 and the other blends used as active layers can be explained by the band alignment of the blend components, excluding an optical effect due to all active layers having the same thickness and similar light penetration depth. As depicted in the band diagram presented in **Figure S3**, Supporting Information, Y6 has a lower HOMO level (-5.80 eV vs vacuum) than F-M, FOIC, or O6T-4F (-5.42 , -5.36 , and -5.32 eV vs vacuum). This means that Y6 in combination with PM6 is the only acceptor herein tested with a HOMO level below the HOMO level of its correspondent donor. This is likely to result in an efficient hole transfer from the Y6-acceptor to the PM6-donor.^[29,34] Thus, at the donor/acceptor interface charge recombination may be reduced, being this a key factor in photoanodes, lacking HTL compared to OPVs. The ETL still plays a crucial role in facilitating the movement and extraction of the electrons

Figure 1. a) Molecular structures of the polymer donors and non-fullerene acceptors studied in this work. b) Cyclic voltammetry curves recorded in a 3-electrode configuration, using an aqueous solution of 1 M KBI with 0.2 M Na_2SO_3 as hole scavenger ($\text{pH} = 9$) as the electrolyte, with a scan rate of 50.0 mV s^{-1} , under chopped simulated solar light illumination conditions (AM 1.5G, 100 mW cm^{-2}). c) $\text{EQE}_{1.23\text{VRHE}}$ spectra of the same samples, measured in a similar configuration at $1.23 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$ applied potential. The indicated photocurrent corresponds to the calculated one based on the integrated $\text{EQE}_{1.23\text{VRHE}}$ spectra and real AM 1.5 G solar illumination.

generated in the active layer. Zinc oxide (ZnO) is frequently employed as the ETL positioned between the indium tin oxide (ITO) and the organic active layers within the OPV structure. ZnO fabricated by sol-gel means was utilized in all the aforementioned photoanode scenarios, replacing the more commonly employed ZnO nanoparticles (np-ZnO). Figure S4, Supporting Information, shows the comparative of the cyclic voltammetry for the photoanodes using sol-gel ZnO and ZnO nanoparticles (np-ZnO), where the superior performance of the sol-gel ZnO is observed. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) Figure S5, Supporting Information, reveals a detachment of the organic active layer from the ETL when np-ZnO is used, correlated to where a pinhole in the active layer is present. Similar irreversible damage has been observed in previous studies, also attributed to ETL modifications.^[22]

2.2. Computational Simulation of the OPEC/OPV Tandem Optimal Structure

Given the large photogenerated power (the product of photocurrent and photovoltage) exhibited by PM6:Y6 as a photoanode compared to the other blends studied, we consider the fabrication of a series-connected tandem structure^[3,39–41] based on employing this high-performance blend in a semitransparent photoanode connected to an OPV cell. This way, by forming the tandem structure, we can form a monolithic structure providing enough photovoltage to drive

the water-splitting reaction, and also maximize the electrochemically active surface (compared to i.e. an OPV cell side-by-side to a photoanode). To identify the most suitable back OPV cell within a series-connected tandem structure, with a focus on achieving the highest photocurrent, we employed a standard-inverse approach coupled with the transfer matrix method.^[3,6,42] Detailed information on our model is available in the Supporting Information. In the OPEC/OPV tandem series configuration, it is essential to match the photocurrent densities of both systems at their respective maximum power points.^[41] Adhering to this requirement and considering the optical properties of each layer (Figure S6, Supporting Information), we systematically assessed the performance of four different photoactive layers for the back OPV cell. The front photoanode was consistently set to 100 nm of PM6:Y6. In this optimization process, we varied the thickness of the back OPV layer to maximize the J_{sc} (short-circuit current of the OPV cell), the PCE of the back cell, and the resulting J_{total} of the tandem configuration (where $J_{\text{total}} = \min[J_{1.23\text{VRHE}}, J_{\text{sc}}]$, and $J_{1.23\text{VRHE}}$ is the photogenerated current of the photoanode at $1.23 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$). Our numerical analysis, presented in Table S3, Supporting Information, indicates that the PM6:Y6 blend as the photoactive layer for the back subcell emerges as the optimal choice. This particular configuration demonstrates the highest PCE and J_{sc} values within the tandem series structure, confirming its superiority for the intended application. Figure 2a shows a schematic representation of the proposed tandem structure where the light propagates first through the

Figure 2. a) Schematic representation of the modeled structure. b) Contour plot of the total short-circuit current (J_{sc}) of both OPEC and OPV. The model takes into account the current balance criteria of the series connection ($J_{total} = \min[J_{1.23VRHE}, J_{sc}]$). Black dots indicate the fabricated photoanode samples 40, 60, 75, and 100 nm. The thickness of the back OPV cell was fixed to be 100 nm. At this thickness, the OPV has a maximum in J_{sc} when it is modeled as an independent system (Figure S7, Supporting Information).

Table 1. Fabricated photoanodes with different PM6:Y6 thicknesses, together with the fixed value for the PM6:Y6 OPV.

Thickness front OPEC (nm)	Thickness back OPV (nm)	$J_{1.23VRHE}$ OPEC (mA/cm^2)	J_{sc} OPV (mA/cm^2)	J_{total} Tandem (mA/cm^2)
40	100	7.55	16.25	7.55
60	100	10.37	13.81	10.37
75	100	12.38	12.27	12.27
100	100	15.53	10.11	10.81

Note: The prospected short-circuit currents are presented, and the total tandem photocurrent is considered to be the least among both absorbers.

electrolyte, then the PM6:Y6 photoanode, and later reaches the OPV cell. In addition, the contour map in Figure 2b demonstrates that the maximum tandem photocurrents are achieved for photoanodes with thicknesses ranging from 60 to 80 nm, almost irrespective of the back OPV cell thickness. Consequently, for the rear OPV cell, we opted to set the thickness to 100 nm, where the OPV cells have an optimal performance in terms of fill factor. In addition, The computed density current as a function of the PM6:Y6 thickness for the OPV cell structure, shown in Figure S7, Supporting Information, exhibits a clear maximum at 100 nm. Subsequently, 40, 60, 75, and 100 nm thick PM6:Y6 photoanodes were selected and paired with 100 nm thick PM6:Y6 OPV cells. The effective performance of the rear OPV cell is significantly linked to the transparency of the front photoanodes.^[3] To underscore this point, Figure S8, Supporting Information, illustrates the computed transmission spectra of the proposed front photoanodes, revealing values of up to 40% of the light reaching the back OPV cell.

The computed photocurrent for each element and the entire tandem structure under short-circuit conditions are presented in Table 1. Simulated EQE for the photoanode polarized at 1.23 V_{RHE} (blue) and for the solar cell at 0 V applied bias for the different thicknesses of front photoanode can be seen in Figure S9, Supporting Information. The tandem structure achieves optimal density current balance with a combination of 75 nm of PM6:Y6 front photoanode and 100 nm thick rear OPV, resulting in a computed current density of 12.27 mA/cm^2 .

2.3. Experimental Results

Fabricated PM6:Y6 photoanodes with thicknesses of 40, 60, 75, and 100 nm are shown in Figure 3a, together with their corresponding transmittance spectra. The darker color of the samples indicates a thicker layer, clearly reflecting increased absorption across the broad visible spectrum. Photoelectrochemical cell measurements demonstrate that higher absorption translates into elevated photocurrents generated at 1.23 V_{RHE} , ranging from 9.2 to 12.5 mA/cm^2 (Figure 3b and Table 2).

The cyclic voltammograms exhibit changes in response to the thickness of the absorber layer, revealing a lower slope in the 0.6–1 V_{RHE} range as the absorber layer thickness. This suggests an increase in transport resistances due to the thicker organic film,^[43] while the onset voltage remains stable at around 0.4 V_{RHE} . These samples demonstrated the capability to sustain the oxidative reaction for several minutes with minor degradation. The $\text{EQE}_{1.23VRHE}$ measurements for these samples, presented in Figure S10, Supporting Information, confirm the lesser absorption and conversion capabilities of the thinner-deposited photoanodes, as expected.

Upon tandem assembly, the OPV, serving as the second element, exhibits approximately half of its short-circuit photocurrent, reducing from 24.6 mA/cm^2 to 13.1, 11.1, 10.4, and 8.3 mA/cm^2 when paired with 40, 60, 75, or 100 nm thick PM6:Y6 photoanodes (Figure 3c and Table 2). It is noteworthy that the OPV's photovoltage diminishes simultaneously as less light reaches the absorber,^[44] a typical solar cell behavior. This effect has, as an implication, a slightly reduced voltage shift upon tandem formation, with open-circuit voltages decreasing from almost 820 to 792 mV.

The selected transparent PM6:Y6 photoanode, optimized at a thickness of 75 nm, was electrically connected or left unconnected to the OPV cell at its back, and the tandem structure was measured (Figure 3d). Remarkably, it exhibited a photocurrent of 7.1 mA/cm^2 at 0 V_{RHE} , record-setting for an organic-based tandem photoanode.^[35] Additionally, onset voltages more cathodic than $-0.4 V_{RHE}$ were achieved, indicating a potential 1.6 V more cathodic than the thermodynamic potential of the oxygen evolution reaction (OER). The photovoltage shift induced by the OPV solar cell measured 713 mV at 7.1 mA/cm^2 or almost 800 mV at 2 mA/cm^2 , aligning with the open-circuit potential measured for the OPV cells (Figure 3c).

Figure 3. a) UV-Vis transmittance of the 4 different thickness fabricated OPEC photoanodes based on 40, 60, 75, and 100 nm thick PM6:Y6 blend layers. Inset: images of the corresponding photoanodes. b) Cyclic voltammetry curves of the 4 different-thickness photoanodes. c) J - V curves of an OPV cell based on PM6:Y6 having the photoanodes presented in a) and b) placed in front, acting as filters. d) Cyclic voltammetry of a PM6:Y6 optimized photoanode connected or not to a PM6:Y6 OPV solar cell. Voltammetries were recorded in a 3-electrode configuration, using an aqueous solution of 1 M KBi with 0.2 M Na_2SO_3 as hole scavenger ($\text{pH} = 9$) as the electrolyte, under simulated solar light illumination conditions ($\text{AM} 1.5\text{G}$, 100 mW cm^{-2}). Parameters extracted from b) and c) are presented in Table 2.

3. Conclusions

In the exploration of various donor/acceptor blends (including PTB7-Th:FOIC, PTB7-Th:O6T-4F, PM6:Y6, and PM6:FM), conventional for organic photovoltaic (OPV) solar cells, PM6:Y6 has emerged as best-performing blend for oxidative reactions, achieving up to 16.8 mA cm^{-2} at $1.23 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$. Light distribution in a double-organic tandem structure has been computationally maximized by optimizing the photoanode's active layer thickness. For the first time, an OPEC/OPV fully organic tandem structure has been formed, showcasing photocurrents of 7.1 mA cm^{-2} at 0 V_{RHE} , onset voltages more cathodic than

$-0.4 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$, and photogenerated voltages of 1.6 V compared to the OER thermodynamic potential.

The tunability of the band gap and the facile solution-based fabrication of organic absorbers, coupled with mild processing temperatures and the herein-achieved overall tandem photovoltages, position these materials for bias-free solar synthetic fuels technologies, overcoming a primary limitation of metal-oxide photoanodes: the generation of significant photocurrents.

4. Experimental Section

Detailed information related to the synthesis of active electrodes, physicochemical characterization, and electrochemical evaluation of bifunctional electrodes towards UOR and supercapacitor application is provided in Supporting Information.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Table 2. Fabricated photoanodes with different PM6:Y6 thicknesses, together with the fixed value for the PM6:Y6 OPV.

Thickness (nm)	Front OPEC			Back OPV				
	$J_{1.23\text{VRHE}}$ (mA cm^{-2})	J_{EQE} (mA cm^{-2})	PCE_{OPEC} (%)	Thickness (nm)	J_{SC} (mA cm^{-2})	V_{OC} (V)	FF (%)	PCE_{OPV} (%)
40	9.2	8.3	2.86	100	13.1	0.794	66.0	6.86
60	11.6	10.9	3.06	100	11.1	0.805	63.8	5.70
75	12.0	11.4	3.27	100	10.4	0.806	65.1	5.46
100	12.5	13.1	3.32	100	8.3	0.815	61.0	4.10

Note: The measured various parameters are presented, corresponding to the results presented in Figure 3. The V_{OC} of the front OPEC has not been presented as the current tends to zero, but does not define a clear V_{OC} . Even so, a V_{ON} (onset potential) for the electrochemical reaction is similar for all samples, about $0.4 \text{ V}_{\text{RHE}}$.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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- [1] C. Ros, T. Andreu, J. R. Morante, *J. Mater. Chem. A Mater.* **2020**, *8*, 10625.
- [2] X. Shi, H. Jeong, S. J. Oh, M. Ma, K. Zhang, J. Kwon, I. T. Choi, I. Y. Choi, H. K. Kim, J. K. Kim, J. H. Park, *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, *7*, 11943.
- [3] C. G. Ferreira, C. Sansierra, F. Bernal-Texca, M. Zhang, C. Ros, J. Martorell, *Energy Environ. Mater.* **2024**, *7*, e12679.
- [4] Q. Shi, S. Murcia-López, P. Tang, C. Flox, J. R. Morante, Z. Bian, H. Wang, T. Andreu, *ACS Catal.* **2018**, *8*, 3331.
- [5] V. F. Kunzelmann, C. M. Jiang, I. Ihrke, E. Sirotti, T. Rieth, A. Henning, J. Eichhorn, I. D. Sharp, *J. Mater. Chem. A Mater.* **2022**, *10*, 12026.
- [6] L. Geronimo, C. Ferreira, V. Gacha, D. Raptis, J. Martorell, C. Ros, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2024**, *7*, 1792.
- [7] C. Fàbrega, S. Murcia-López, D. Monllor-Satoca, J. D. Prades, M. D. Hernández-Alonso, G. Penelas, J. R. Morante, T. Andreu, *Appl. Catal. B* **2016**, *189*, 133.
- [8] A. Fujishima, K. Honda, *Nature* **1972**, *238*, 37.
- [9] C. Ros, C. Fabrega, D. Monllor-Satoca, M. D. Hernández-Alonso, G. Penelas-Pérez, J. R. Morante, T. Andreu, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2018**, *122*, 3295.
- [10] M. Cao, K. Yao, C. Wu, J. Huang, W. Yang, L. Zhang, F. Lei, Y. Sun, L. Wang, Y. Shen, *ACS Appl. Energy Mater.* **2018**, *1*, 6497.
- [11] K. Sivula, *ChemCatChem* **2014**, *6*, 2796.
- [12] C. Ros, T. Andreu, M. D. Hernández-Alonso, G. Penelas-Pérez, J. Arbiol, J. R. Morante, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2017**, *9*, 17932.
- [13] C. Ros, T. Andreu, J. David, J. Arbiol, J. R. Morante, *J. Mater. Chem. A Mater.* **2019**, *7*, 21892.
- [14] S. Hu, M. R. Shaner, J. A. Beardslee, M. Lichterman, B. S. Brunschwig, N. S. Lewis, *Science* **2014**, *344*, 1005.
- [15] F. Yang, A. C. Nielander, R. L. Grimm, N. S. Lewis, *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2016**, *120*, 6989.
- [16] C. Ros, T. Andreu, S. Giraldo, Y. Sánchez, J. R. Morante, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* **2016**, *158*, 184.
- [17] C. Ros, T. Andreu, S. Giraldo, V. Izquierdo-Roca, E. Saucedo, J. R. Morante, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2018**, *10*, 13425.
- [18] L. Rovelli, S. D. Tilley, K. Sivula, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2013**, *5*, 8018.
- [19] P. De Luna, C. Hahn, D. Higgins, S. A. Jaffer, T. F. Jaramillo, E. H. Sargent, *Science* **2019**, *364*, eaav3506.
- [20] T. J. Jacobsson, *Energ. Environ. Sci.* **2018**, *11*, 1977.
- [21] J. Fu, P. W. K. Fong, H. Liu, C. S. Huang, X. Lu, S. Lu, M. Abdelsamie, T. Kodalle, C. M. Sutter-Fella, Y. Yang, G. Li, *Nat. Commun.* **2023**, *14*, 1760.
- [22] C. T. Lin, C. T. Hsieh, T. J. Macdonald, J. F. Chang, P. C. Lin, H. Cha, L. Steier, A. Wadsworth, I. McCulloch, C. C. Chueh, J. R. Durrant, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2022**, *32*(40), 1.
- [23] C. Xie, X. Zeng, C. Li, X. Sun, S. Liang, H. Huang, B. Deng, X. Wen, G. Zhang, P. You, C. Yang, Y. Han, S. Li, G. Lu, H. Hu, N. Li, Y. Chen, *Energ. Environ. Sci.* **2024**, *17*, 2441.
- [24] T. H. Lee, R. R. Rao, R. A. Pacalaj, A. A. Wilson, J. R. Durrant, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2022**, *12*, 2103698.
- [25] Z. C. Wen, H. Yin, X. T. Hao, *Surfaces Interfaces* **2021**, *23*, 100921.
- [26] Q. Guo, Q. Guo, Y. Geng, A. Tang, M. Zhang, M. Du, X. Sun, E. Zhou, *Mater. Chem. Front.* **2021**, *5*, 3257.
- [27] L. Perdigón-Toro, H. Zhang, A. Markina, J. Yuan, S. M. Hosseini, C. M. Wolff, G. Zuo, M. Stollerfoht, Y. Zou, F. Gao, D. Andrienko, S. Shoaee, D. Neher, *Adv. Mater.* **2020**, *32*, e1906763.
- [28] Q. Liu, L. G. Gerling, F. Bernal-Texca, J. Toudert, T. Li, X. Zhan, J. Martorell, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2020**, *10*(17), 1.
- [29] L. Bolzonello, F. Bernal-Texca, L. G. Gerling, J. Ockova, E. Collini, J. Martorell, N. F. Van Hulst, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2021**, *12*, 3983.
- [30] J. M. Yu, J.-W. Jang, *Catalysts* **2023**, *13*, 814.
- [31] H. H. Cho, L. Yao, J. H. Yum, Y. Liu, F. Boudoire, R. A. Wells, N. Guijarro, A. Sekar, K. Sivula, *Nat. Catal.* **2021**, *4*, 431.
- [32] A. Sekar, J. M. Moreno-Naranjo, Y. Liu, J.-H. Yum, B. P. Darwich, H.-H. Cho, N. Guijarro, L. Yao, K. Sivula, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2022**, *14*, 8191.
- [33] T. N. Das, R. E. Huie, P. Neta, *J. Phys. Chem. A* **1999**, *103*, 3581.
- [34] T. H. Lee, S. A. J. Hillman, S. Gonzalez-Carrero, A. Difilippo, J. R. Durrant, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2023**, *13*, 2300400.
- [35] L. Yao, A. Rahmanudin, N. Guijarro, K. Sivula, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2018**, *8*(32), 1.
- [36] F. Bernal-Texca, J. Martorell, *Sol. RRL* **2024**, *8*, 2300728.
- [37] Z. Wu, H. Yin, G. Li, Z. Ji, *Org. Electron.* **2024**, *129*, 107060.
- [38] X. Ma, Z. Xiao, Q. An, M. Zhang, Z. Hu, J. Wang, L. Ding, F. Zhang, *J. Mater. Chem. A Mater.* **2018**, *6*, 21485.
- [39] A. Alfano, A. Mezzetti, F. Fumagalli, C. Tao, E. Rovera, A. Petrozza, F. Di Fonzo, *IScience* **2021**, *24*, 102463.
- [40] Y. H. Lai, D. W. Palm, E. Reisner, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2015**, *5*(24), 1.
- [41] J. Brillet, M. Comuz, F. Le Formal, J. H. Yum, M. Grätzel, K. Sivula, *J. Mater. Res.* **2010**, *25*, 17.
- [42] G. Martínez-Denegri, C. G. Ferreira, M. A. Ruiz-Preciado, P. Fassi, M. Kramarenko, U. W. Paetzold, J. Martorell, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2022**, *12*, 2201473.
- [43] X. Elias, Q. Liu, C. Gimbert-Suriñach, R. Matheu, P. Mantilla-Perez, A. Martínez-Otero, X. Sala, J. Martorell, A. Llobet, *ACS Catal.* **2016**, *6*, 3310.
- [44] I. Gelmetti, N. F. Montcada, A. Pérez-Rodríguez, E. Barrena, C. Ocal, I. García-Benito, A. Molina-Ontoria, N. Martín, A. Vidal-Ferran, E. Palomares, *Energ. Environ. Sci.* **2019**, *12*, 1309.